

Development of a LW-SMR dry containment CFD model with containmentFOAM

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Abstract

The Horizon Euratom SASPAM-SA Project aims to explore the transferability of knowledge from large LWRs to water-cooled SMRs. More specifically, the project investigates the ability of different codes to simulate the driving phenomena of potential Severe Accident sequences for two different “generic” SMRs. The “Design II” represents a dry containment with several passive safety features—a Pressure Suppression System (PSS), among others—based on information available in the open literature. One of the codes being evaluated in the framework of SASPAM-SA is containmentFOAM, an open-source CFD package based on OpenFOAM developed by Forschungszentrum Jülich. Since containmentFOAM was initially conceived to simulate conventional PWRs, a number of upgrades are being implemented based on the assessment of the SA sequences simulated in SASPAM-SA to tailor the code to LW-SMRs' specific needs. In particular, the paper summarises the validation and a preliminary application of a multi-fidelity coupling of containmentFOAM (CFD) and Modelica (system code) to represent the main thermo-fluid dynamic processes of PSSs. The validation showed a quantitative and qualitative agreement with the experimental measurements of the PPOOLEX MIX experimental series. Additionally, the pressure-coupling showed robust numerical stability, also confirmed for the preliminary calculations at plant scale.

1. Introduction

One of the most recent energy outlooks published by the Nuclear Energy Agency (NEA) postulated the installation of up to 400 GW of Small Modular Reactors (SMR) [1]. Of all the concepts under consideration, Light Water SMRs (LW-SMRs) are the most likely to be deployed in the near future. These concepts generally share characteristics with currently operating large-LWRs, as well as specific features related to their evolutionary designs, which provide safety benefits that enhance the first three levels of the Defence-in-Depth (DiD) principles [2], [3]. The path from the conceptualization [4] to the licensed concept [5] of a reactor is complex, efforts-intensive and time consuming. The process involves numerous interactions between designers and regulators and may also require the interaction with other stakeholders (e.g. conducting new experiments). Indeed, even with a plant designed with advanced safety features that reinforce the first three DiD levels, the regulators require the incorporation of independent features for Severe Accident (SA) prevention and mitigation into its design (DiD level 4). Consequently, certain scenarios that could result in SAs must be postulated and studied deterministically (see [2] for more information). Relatedly, the Horizon Euratom SASPAM-SA Project [6], [7], coordinated by ENEA (Italy), addresses the identification of potential postulated SA sequences of two generic concepts with representative features for a range of LW-SMRs. The so-called Design-I in SASPAM-SA features a generic integral Pressure Water Reactor (i-PWR) of about 60 MWe embedded in a containment submerged in a pool. The Design-II consists of a generic integral i-PWR of about 300 MWe, a dry containment and several passive systems. The postulation of different SA sequences for each design has been summarised in [8].

Simulation tools perform a central role in the safety justification and demonstration of innovative designs and safety systems, and therefore its applicability must be continuously re-evaluated. Indeed, one of the main objectives of SASPAM-SA is to investigate the applicability of the know-how for large-LWRs to LW-SMR, with a focus on identifying potential phenomenological differences of relevance for postulated SA progressions and the ability of the SA codes to replicate the expected phenomena. As shown in [8], most of the SASPAM-SA activities have been performed with SA codes using the Lumped Parameter (LP) approach. However, one partner per generic design uses a Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) code to complement the evaluation of the applicability of the available SA codes to postulated LW-SMR SA scenarios.

The governing equations of CFD do not contain lengths or reference scales, meaning the CFD method can, in principle, be transferred between different applications and scales [9]. This feature is particularly important for situations where the postulated sequences are characterized by conditions with no engineering correlations yet available. Additionally, the CFD codes may reveal the influence of challenging phenomena for the LP approach, such as natural circulation driven by low-density differences or flows with an intrinsic 3D nature. However, due to the complex multi-scale and multi-physic phenomena associated with the postulated scenarios, the direct application of general-purpose CFD codes to nuclear safety analysis is not straightforward. Indeed, containmentFOAM [10], the open-source CFD package based on OpenFOAM [11] that will be used in this work, has been tailored towards the needs of containment SA analysis for conventional large PWRs.

Therefore, as holds true for the SA codes using the LP approach, the applicability of the modelling basis of containmentFOAM to the postulated scenarios of SASPAM-SA must be also evaluated. This evaluation towards the use of containmentFOAM to simulate the containment behaviour of the SASPAM-SA Design II is the main purpose of the paper. In the next section, the postulated scenarios calculated in SASPAM-SA are used to identify the potential limitations of containmentFOAM for the foreseen technical scale application. Section 3 summarises one of the upgrades implemented in the code, a coupling scheme used to model one of the passive safety systems of Design-II, including the current validation status of the coupling. Last, section 4 describes the efforts to develop a containmentFOAM model of Design II as similar as possible to the models developed with SA codes. The paper is closed with the preliminary simulation of one of the postulated sequences, designed to set the basis of a strategy to perform insightful comparisons between the LP codes and containmentFOAM.

2. containmentFOAM development needs based on SASPAM-SA scenarios

This section of the paper is conceived to provide the minimum amount of information to make it self explanatory while keeping the expected brevity of the article. Specifically, it provides the modelling basis of containmentFOAM [10], the main safety features of the SASPAM-SA Design 2 LW-SMR [12], [13], which is a generic IRIS-SMR defined in [14], and the main characteristics of the postulated SA sequences [8]. The specifications of both generic SASPAM-SA designs were determined in the Work Package (WP) 2 based on open literature and engineering judgment [15].

containmentFOAM is an open-source CFD package based on OpenFOAM [11] developed in Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH (FZJ). Although the first references on containmentFOAM development are relatively recent [16], the code was built on set of models for containment applications developed and validated during more than 10 years using ANSYS CFX [17]. These models development was conceived with the clear target of enabling their application at plant scale, where the small scales of the physics are combined with the larges scales of the containment building

and the long duration of accidental sequences. Therefore, tailoring the models to the expected scenario was a primary requirement to balance the reliable representation of the physics with their numerical efficiency. Specifically, containmentFOAM has been tailored to towards the needs of containment SA analysis for conventional large PWRs, a Generic PWR-KWU as the one described in [18].

From the characteristics summarised in Table 1 and the insights of decades of research in wall condensation [19], it can be argued that for a postulated SA in large PWRs the liquid phase does not play a primary role in the containment thermal hydraulics. Accordingly, containmentFOAM used a single-phase approach where the liquid phase within the containment was considered a passive scalar and was excluded from the simulation domain upon condensation on the walls. Most of the code developments focused on achieving a detailed characterization of the heat and mass transport phenomena in the multi-species gas phase within the containment. This was achieved by incorporating specific models for wall condensation, turbulent buoyancy-driven flows, aerosol deposition, and engineering systems, among others. As summarised in Table 1, the SASPAM-SA generic design brings scenarios with distinct characteristics, motivating the re-evaluation of the code’s general modelling approach.

The code applicability evaluation was performed before developing a containment model for the SASPAM-SA Design-II. It was based on a detailed analysis of the characteristics of the postulated Design Basis Accident (DBA) and SA sequences calculated by SA codes, such as ASTEC and MELCOR. The description of the main characteristics of the sequences will be based on the scenarios represented in Figure 1, highlighting the relevant features from a containmentFOAM perspective (more details available in [12], [20]). Generally, the accident evolution is driven by the pressure differences of three connected “systems”, highlighted in Figure 1: the Reactor Pressure Vessel (RPV) – P_1 , the DryWell (DW)– P_2 , and the Pressure Suppression System (PSS) – P_3 .

Figure 1. Representation of different phases of a DVI break in SASPAM-SA Design-II. In the picture: Pressure Suppression System (PSS), Automatic Depressurization System (ADS), Long-term Gravity Make-up System (LGMS), Quench Tank (QT), and Emergency Borated Tanks (EBT)

Table 1. Characteristic values of a conventional large PWR and two LW-SMRs from [8] and [18]

Design	Ratio reactor power to containment free volume	Pressure peak after blowdown	Maximum free volume occupied by liquid
Generic PWR-KWU	0.05 $\left(\frac{MW_t}{m^3}\right)$	< 4 bar	negligible
SASPAM-SA Design-1	0.88 $\left(\frac{MW_t}{m^3}\right)$	< 40 bar	Up to 40%
SASPAM-SA Design-2	0.27 $\left(\frac{MW_t}{m^3}\right)$	< 12.5 bar	Up to 15%

The scheme on the left of Figure 1 represent the main flow transport process for the passive response of the Design II to a postulated break in the reactor coolant system (blowdown phase). Commonly, LW-SMRs response to a break is to minimise the mass of water release from the RPV. In both generic design of SASPAM-SA, this happens by equalising the pressure of of the RPV (P_1) and the DW (P_3) as fast as possible via Automatic Depressurization Systems (ADS). The first challenge for the modelling basis of containmentFOAM, arising from the chain of events described above, is related to the physics of the wall condensation. For the range of pressures expected in conventional large reactors, the presence of Non-Condensable Gases (NCGs) in the boundary layer is the main thermal resistance to delimit the condensation rates [17], [19]. However, the wall condensation with the characteristics of the LW-SMRs summarised in Table 1, with much higher steam concentrations, are characterised by the film wise condensation regime [21] where the main thermal resistance to delimit the condensation rates is the liquid film. This motivates the need for an extension of the wall condensation models and the validation matrix of containmentFOAM, which is currently ongoing.

The second relevant feature of Desing II to be considered in this discussion is the actuation of the PSS. The pressure rise within the containment will induce a pressure difference, facilitating the flow from the Drywell (P_2) to the PSS (P_3), as depicted in Figure 1. The steam purged into the PSS will condense in the subcooled pool, thereby restricting the pressure increase in the Drywell. The backpressure at the PSS, with its gas space connected to the LGMS, will govern the flow from the Drywell to the PSS. As the PSS is designed to condense all the steam while remaining subcooled, the pressure increase in the PSS will be characterized by the buildup of NCGs in its gas space.

The maximum pressure reached in the drywell for a DBA happens at the same time as the pressure equalisation with the RPV ($P_1 \approx P_2$). Subsequently, the pressures in the RPV and Drywell begin to decrease due to the combined effects of the core cooling systems and wall condensation, respectively. However, these cooling processes do not impact the PSS and LGMS (P_3). At a certain point of the transient, the higher pressure at the PSS will be large enough to push back water from the PSS to the drywell, with the containment evolving from the left to the right picture of Figure 1. To reach the expected stable cooling of a standard DBA sequence, the water level in the reactor cavity must be above the location of the break, closing the long-term cooling loop. This is a necessary condition to avoid a SA with the generation and release of hydrogen to the DW. Therefore, it is clear that the liquid phase plays a central role on the long-term response of the Design-II to a postulated accident. Furthermore, as shown in Table 1, the liquid occupies more than a 10% of the containment free volume in Design II and up to a 40% in Design I. The larger relevance of the liquid phase motivates the second principal upgrade of the current multi-species single-phase solver of containmentFOAM with a two-phase volume of fluid approach [22].

The last remarkable characteristic of the described sequence of Design II is the strong link of the pressures of three different systems. The mass and energy transfer processes that govern the pressure evolution in each separate system influence one another. Consequently, using different codes to simulate the primary system, the containment, or the safety systems, which is a common approach for conventional PWRs, would present greater limitations for LW-SMRs. Although the coupled simulation of the RPV, Drywell, and PSS provides clear advantages in terms of calculation representativeness, it also entails a substantial increase in computational cost. Therefore, for the technical scale application anticipated in this work, it is impractical to apply the same level of detail to all systems. Having the flexibility to cleverly decide where to put the details, i.e., to enable multi-scale calculations, arises as an essential feature for containmentFOAM. The upgrade of containmentFOAM to enable coupled calculation will be the main focus of the sections of the paper to follow.

3. Coupling description and validation

This section describes the ongoing work to support a multi-scale modelling approach by coupling containmentFOAM with simplified models of the safety systems. In particular, the objective would be to use a high fidelity to represent the DW, using containmentFOAM, and a lower fidelity to represent the PSS, with OpenModelica [23]. The general characteristics of the coupling are described in a first subsection, followed by a summary of its current validation status.

3.1 Coupling characteristics

The core aspect of the coupling approach is the application of the Functional Mock-up Interface (FMI) 2.0 standard [24] to facilitate the exchange of information between containmentFOAM and the system-code-like model of the PSS. The PSS model was created and exported as an executable simulator, known as a Functional Mock-up Unit (FMU), using OpenModelica. The FMI standard, widely utilised in the automotive and aerospace industries, provides a transparent and open interface that allows multiple individuals to develop FMUs that can be integrated with the same comprehensive model. The three main features of this coupling approach are as follows:

- The FMI standard and Modelica are aligned with the open-source nature of containmentFOAM. The foundational aim of Modelica was to integrate various languages designed for solving systems of differential and algebraic equations for different purposes, thereby creating a new open language that enhances collaboration across different fields [23]. The same principle applies to FMI coupling, which is an open standard for exchanging information between codes. Any pair of simulation tools adapted to support the FMI standard can be easily interconnected [24].
- Most of the coupling solutions in the nuclear industry are code specific, and usually require access to the source code of proprietary tools. On the contrary, as it is defined as a standard for the exchange of information, FMI compatibility is code agnostic.
- The combination of these two features provides complete modularity to the proposed coupling scheme. Various institutions can independently develop FMUs for different purposes, and these can be seamlessly integrated to solve a comprehensive problem facilitated by the FMI standard.

Currently, the coupling scheme employs a domain decomposition approach that facilitates pressure-velocity coupling for uni-directional fluid flow. It allows low-fidelity and CFD models to exchange

fields such as species mass, energy, and transported quantities. The scheme utilises a semi-implicit method with Picard iterations for time discretisation, supporting multiple serial updates of field values until convergence is achieved. Additionally, it accommodates sub-cycling on the FMU side if only an explicit forward Euler solver is available for the Modelica model. Parallel processing capabilities and simulation restart functionalities are integrated into the coupling framework. Its implementation is a "native" extension of the main containmentFOAM solver loop, utilising only the FMI Library [24] and the OpenFOAM-provided parallel MPI-based communication mechanisms. As shown in [25], the coupling scheme has undergone systematic verification to ensure numerical stability and conservativeness, not repeated here for the sake of brevity.

3.2 Validation based on the PPOOLEX-MIX Series

The validation presented in this sub-section aims to assess and showcase the performance of the described coupling in a scenario close to the technical scale application foreseen in SASPAM-SA. Specifically, it focuses on simulating the transport of the gas mixture from the DW to the PSS during the blowdown phase, which is the most demanding in terms of stability for the pressure coupling. The validation has been based on the MIX experimental series performed in PPOOLEX, a test facility designed and constructed by the Lappeenranta University of Technology [26]. PPOOLEX features a drywell connected by a blowdown pipe to a wetwell, which contains a water pool, providing a suitable analogy with the DW and the PSS of SASPAM-SA Design II.

The detailed description of the facility, the experiments, and the modelling strategy are given in [20]. The information provided here summarises the key aspects of the validation exercise to illustrate the performance of the coupling scheme. The drywell of PPOOLEX and the blowdown pipe are modelled with containmentFOAM, using a relatively coarse mesh of approximately 160k cells. The wetwell is modelled with an FMU developed using as a basis the ThermoPower library [27] of OpenModelica. The FMU is a simple 0D model containing water and gas in non-equilibrium within a single computational node. The FMI pressure coupling interface between containmentFOAM and the FMU is located at the exit of the blowdown pipe¹. Since the water pool of PPOOLEX is subcooled, all the steam transported from the CFD side is immediately condensed in the water phase of the FMU. The NCGs flowing down to the wetwell are accumulated in the gas phase of the FMU.

The experiments of the PPOOLEX MIX series [26] were designed to investigate different flow regimes for the direct contact condensation process associated to the injection of steam to a subcooled pool. All the MIX experiments had three separated phases that can be induced from the experimental data given with markers in Figure 2 and Figure 3. The first phase lasts approximately 500 seconds and is characterised by a rapid pressure increase induced by the injection of high flow rates of steam to the drywell, which induces the transport and accumulation of the NCGs in the wetwell. Later, the steam mass flow rate decreases for a second phase, which is characterised by moderated pressure and increases in pool average temperature. Last, the steam mass flow rate to the drywell is increased again, accelerating the pressurisation and the pool heating up. The three experiments illustrated at Figure 2 and Figure 3 had different steam mass flow rates and durations for each of these phases.

¹ The main difference between the model used in [20] and the one presented here is the definition of a second coupling interface between containmentFOAM and the FMU. Specifically, at the 0.1 m steel plate used to separate the Drywell and the gas space of the Wetwell at PPOOLEX. The temperature calculated by containmentFOAM was used to compute a heat flux from the Drywell to the gas space of the Wetwell. This implementation, consistent with the actual behaviour of the facility, allowed to reproduce the experimental pressure, which was previously underestimated in [20].

The simulation results are plotted with continuous lines in Figure 2 and Figure 3, with the results of the CFD labelled as ‘DW-cFoam’ and all the other lines obtained from the FMU. The simulation was performed on a cluster with two processors (Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2637v2 @3.50 GHz, 64 GB) and for a total of 16 cores. The performance of the model during the test case in terms of convergence and stability was satisfactory, with running time between 2 and 4 days, depending on the test duration. Furthermore, the simulations mostly reproduced the experimental measurements for all the figures of merit (pressurisation of the drywell, pressurisation of the wetwell, and the heating up of the pool).

Figure 2. Pressure evolution of both coupled systems compared with the PPOOLEX experiments

Figure 3. Pool average temperature predictions compared with the PPOOLEX experimental series

4. Development of the LW-SMR Design II Model and preliminary results

As already mentioned in the introduction, the main objective of FZJ in SASPAM-SA is to complement the insights offered by the simulation performed with SA codes. Since the duration of the complete sequences, in the order of tens of hours, is not affordable in terms of computational cost, the CFD calculations will study selected time windows. Specifically, this section evaluates the plausibility of studying the blowdown phase illustrated in Figure 1, where potential heterogeneities of the NCG distribution between the DW and the PSS or the different wall condensation regimes may have an impact on the system pressurisation. Apart from the evident need to represent the PSS using the

containmentFOAM-Modelica coupling presented in section 3, the model development addresses other challenges, such as the geometry and mesh definitions or the correct implementation of the mass and energy releases to the containment calculated by the SASPAM-SA partners with LP codes. All these issues are summarised below.

Being the objective to compare and complement the SA codes with containmentFOAM results, the definition of the 3D geometry must be consistent with the one used by the LP codes, which was based on a common database developed in SASPAM-SA [15]. Evidently, the quantity of data needed to create a 3D model is larger than to construct a simplified 0D control volume. Therefore, the missing data was induced by engineering judgment. This process resulted in a detailed CAD model of Design II, which was used as a basis for the CFD model. The CAD also helped to identify and rectify some inconsistencies in the geometry database initially used by the LP modellers. The free volume and wall surfaces of the final CAD model had a relative error below 1.2% and 2.8%, respectively.

The geometry of the Design II containment is much simpler than a typical containment of a large PWR. However, the number of tanks and pipes (see Figure 1) complicates the geometry enough to motivate the use of an automatic non-structured mesher. However, the first exploration of these option resulted in a non-optimal mesh in terms of quality and total number of cells. Therefore, the possibility to model the Design II containment with a manually built structured mesh, i.e. hexahedral elements with low non-orthogonality or skewness, is currently being explored. Figure 4 shows a general view of the mesh, with a zoom to the region of the blowdown pipe connecting the DW with the PSS. The current model uses two symmetry planes to model one-quarter of the geometry, with a total number of 610k cells. The basic mesh quality criteria of OpenFOAM are complied with, with minimum face angles larger than 27° and maximum volume changes below 6 [28]. The models include the free volume of the containment (fluid region) and the metallic liner of the SCV (solid region). This mesh should be understood as an intermediate step towards the final model, as the volume occupied by the LGMS, EBT, and QT tanks is not considered yet. However, it helps to evaluate the proposed structured mesh and the coupling with the PSS (implemented again at the end of the blowdown pipe) at the scale of the foreseen plant scale application.

Figure 4. General features of the preliminary containmentFOAM model of SASPAM-SA Design-II

The mass and energy sources to the containment have been implemented as volumetric sources based on the calculations performed by ENEA using the ASTEC code [8]. The selected sequence is the DBA of SASPAM-SA for Design II, a break of the DVI line with all the passive safety systems available. At this sequence, there are two main sources of steam to the DW, the liquid flashed from the break and the steam leaving the QT during the RPV depressurisation by the ADS-1. Only the second break, which had the largest flow rate, was implemented for this preliminary analysis. The steam injection flow rate has been included in Figure 5 c). The final heat sink of the DW is the environment surrounding the SCV. The convective heat transfer from the SCV to the environment is implemented as a Robin type boundary condition, using the heat transfer coefficient calculated by ASTEC ($\sim 10 \text{ W/m}^2\text{-K}$) and an ambient temperature.

The key features of the physical used the single-phase modelling basis of containmentFOAM described in [10] and validated for PWR containments. Figure 5 shows the main variables selected to evaluate the system response, the pressures and temperatures of DW and PSS, and the steam mass balance. The simulation was performed on a cluster with four processors (Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2637v2 @3.50 GHz, 64 GB) and for a total of 32 cores, running the 1000 seconds of the sequence in one and a half days.

As expected, the relatively large steam mass flow rates associated with the blowdown phase induced a pressure increase in the CFD domain. When the pressure difference between the drywell and the gas space of the PSS was enough to overcome the hydrostatic pressure of the water column, a mixture of steam and nitrogen was injected into the PSS. The temperature increase of the liquid of the PSS is not enough to induce significant evaporation rates ($\sim 5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ as seen in Figure 5 b). Thus, the pressure increase at the PSS side was driven by the accumulation of non-condensable gases, which is illustrated on the left of Figure 6. The pressure increase in the DW is consistent with the temperature increase and the accumulation of steam induced from Figure 6, which illustrate with continuous lines the source (from ASTEC) and sinks (sum of wall condensation and steam transport to the PSS) of steam in the CFD domain. The red line of the steam sources is always above the line of the steam sinks, confirming the postulated accumulation of steam. These results are preliminary, as the condensation on concrete structures and the complete steam flash from the break have not been implemented in the model yet.

DW-PSS Pressure coupling

a)

CFD averaged temperature and FMU temperature

b)

Steam mass balance at the DW

c)

Figure 5. Pressure (a) and temperature (b) evolution at the CFD and system code sides. Steam sources (injection) and sinks (condensation and PSS) of the CFD model (c)

Last, it is worth looking at the 3D effects affecting the transport of NCG to the PSS. On the right of Figure 6, the comparison of the nitrogen concentration at the blowdown pipe exit (FMI interface) and the average concentration of the DW (typical information from LP codes) are not identical. This behaviour is clear when looking at the 2D plots of Figure 7 for different moments of the transient. These local 3D effects, affecting the nitrogen transport that is the main process for the pressure build-up, showcase the potential of CFD calculations to complement the results of LP codes. Nevertheless, direct comparison is not possible at this point due to the preliminary nature of these calculations.

Figure 6. Transport of nitrogen from the SCV to the PSS

Figure 7. Nitrogen distribution inside the steel containment vessel

5. Conclusion

The phenomenological differences between the SA scenarios of LW-SMRs and the conventional large PWR (those used as the reference scenarios for the development of containmentFOAM) are driving a re-evaluation of the traditional modelling approach of containmentFOAM. The prioritisation of the code development needs is based on the analysis of the characteristics of the SA sequences postulated in the EU Horizon Project SASPAM-SA.

The work described in this article focused on the need to represent the stronger pressure coupling between the containment and the passive safety systems. This requires a multi-fidelity modelling approach, enabling the simulation of the passive safety systems using a system code approach, which has been implemented by developing a coupling framework for containmentFOAM and OpenModelica using the FMI standard. The coupling has been validated using a set of experiments with phenomena comparable to those of the foreseen plant safety analysis, the PPOOLEX MIX series. The simulation results show a qualitative and quantitative agreement with the experimental measurements, and the numerical stability of the coupling is one of the outputs to highlight.

Implementing the coupling scheme is one step in using containmentFOAM to complement the calculation performed with severe accident codes in the SASPAM-SA framework. Combining the coupling with the work performed for developing the mesh/geometry of the model and for implementing data from the LP codes as boundary conditions allows us to showcase a first plant scale analysis of the blowdown phase. These preliminary simulations already show its ability to identify 3D effects with the potential to influence the system response, analyses that should be improved with the objective of performing insightful comparisons with the LP codes results.

From the modelling basis presented in this article, future works will include the non-represented geometries in the model (concrete floor, LGMS tanks, etc.), extending the one-quarter symmetry to the full-containment model. Furthermore, the implementation of the remaining sources of mass and energy will enable the benchmarking of containmentFOAM and the severe accident codes.

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